

GENDER DIFFERENCE IN TEACHER EFFECTIVENESS OF TEACHER EDUCATORS

Koushik Das

M. Phil Research Scholar, Department of Education, Annamalai University

Dr. R. Gnanadevan

Professor(Rtd.), Department of Education, Annamalai University

Abstract

The present study aimed to compare the male and female teacher educators with respect to teacher effectiveness. It is an ex post-facto study. Survey method with stratified random sampling technique has been employed for the present study. The teacher effectiveness scale standardized by Umme Kulsum (2011) has been adapted to collect the data from the sample. The tool includes five areas of teacher effectiveness such as, preparation and planning for teaching, classroom management, knowledge of subject matter, teacher's characteristics and interpersonal relations. The sample of the study consists of 260 teacher educators working in different B. Ed. Colleges at the west zone of North 24 parganas District in West Bengal, India. The study revealed that the male and female teacher educators do not differ significantly in two dimensions of teacher effectiveness such as, class room management and teacher characteristics. They differ significantly in three dimensions of teacher effectiveness such as preparation and planning for teaching, knowledge of subject matter, and interpersonal relation and all these three dimensions the female teacher educators have high level than the male teacher educators. The study further revealed that the total teacher effectiveness is also high for the female teacher educators than the male teacher educators.

Keywords: *-Teacher educators-Gender difference in teacher effectiveness*

1. INTRODUCTION

Teaching is a noble profession, but in India there is no unique possibility to grow as a teacher. That is why young aspirants are facing lot of challenges as well as teacher education. The teacher educators have the bound duties and responsibilities to create humane and professional teacher to shape future generations. Teachers at all levels in Indian context have to engage themselves with innovations, projects, in-service training programmes, administrative work and so on. So, at present teachers need to polish their skills every day and to perform as multitasking personnel like other profession. Smart teacher can only shape and overcome all the challenges for grooming our next smart generation. School teachers can face the challenges when they have positive mind set for their profession and teacher educators will groom, help them during their training period.

2. NEED AND IMPORTANCE OF THE STUDY

Teacher effectiveness focus on teachers subject mastery, maintain teacher characteristics and utilize skills for planning, preparing and managing their classroom and

building good relationship with students in teachers training colleges which enhances students achievement.

The present study aimed to find out the gender difference in the teacher effectiveness and also the different dimensions of teacher effectiveness. Gender is a social construct that impacts attitudes, roles, responsibilities and behavior patterns of boys and girls, men and women in all societies. Gender relations vary from society to society. It has been the most endemic form of discrimination operating across cultures in developed and developing societies. Education has the inbuilt potential of initiating social change in the context of gender relations. Thus, exploring the gender difference in the teacher effectiveness is a topic worthy of further study in the field of education.

Gender difference in third world countries is a major problem now. From the review of related studies the investigator came to know that at present only very few studies conducted by the researcher with respect to gender difference in teacher effectiveness of teacher educators. The study conducted by Uddin et al. (2020) revealed that there is no significance difference in response on personality between male and female teachers, There is no significance difference in response on subject matter between male and female teachers, There is no significance difference in response on relational competency with students between male and female teachers, There is no significance difference in response on personal competency between male and female teacher, There is no significance difference in response on teaching style between male and female teachers, There is no significance difference in response on class room management style between male and female teachers. The study conducted by Visweswari et al. (2019) indicated that there is a significant difference in teacher effectiveness in order to their gender and locality. Naik et al. (2018) found that, there is no significant mean difference among male and female teachers working in government and private secondary schools located in rural and urban area. It means locality, types of school and sex cannot influence the teacher effectiveness.

Based on the above discussion the investigator felt it is necessary to find out the gender difference in the teacher effectiveness of teacher educators. The present study will be useful for the student teachers as well as teacher educators, because the knowledge about gender difference in teacher effectiveness of teacher educators will enable the teachers and policymakers to plan teaching and learning process keeping in view of the study.

3. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The objective of the study is to find out the significance of difference between male and female teacher educators in the total teacher effectiveness and also the following five dimensions of teacher effectiveness:

- a. *Preparation and planning for teaching*
- b. *Classroom management*
- c. *Knowledge of subject matter*
- d. *Teacher's characteristics and*
- e. *Inter-personal relations.*

Suitable null hypotheses have been formulated and tested the hypotheses with the statistical analysis significance of difference between two mean ('t' test).

4. METHOD OF THE STUDY

The investigator adapted normative survey method for the present study. Nature of the research is ex-post facto study. Here the population of the study were all teacher educators working in teacher's training institutions in the state of West Bengal. From this population the investigator took a chunk of population called sample unit from the district of North 24 Parganas at West Bengal. Stratified random sampling techniques has been followed for the selection of sample from the population. The size of each stratum of the study has been decided based on the principle of disproportionate stratified sample. The sample includes 260 teacher educators from west zone of North 24 Parganas at West Bengal. Teacher effectiveness scale standardized by Umme Kulsum (2011) has been adapted to collect the data from the sample. The tool includes five areas of teacher effectiveness such as, preparation and planning for teaching, classroom management, knowledge of subject matter, teacher's characteristics and interpersonal relations.

5. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Ho: There is no significant difference in the total teacher effectiveness and all the dimensions of teacher effectiveness with respect to gender.

To test the above mentioned hypothesis, 't' test has been applied. The result of the analysis is presented in table-1.

Table-1
't' Value of Different Dimensions of Teacher Effectiveness Scores of Teacher Educators with respect to Gender

Dimensions of Teacher Effectiveness	N	Mean		t-value
		Male	Female	
Preparation and Planning for Teaching	260	69.28	71.73	3.99**
Classroom Management		92.70	91.70	1.15
Knowledge of Subject matter		52.46	54.21	6.62**
Teacher Characteristics		101.71	102.65	0.53
Interpersonal Relation		70.71	71.00	3.49**
Total Teacher Effectiveness		385.86	391.28	2.49*

Note:*p<.05, **p<.01

Comparison of Mean Difference in the Preparation and Planning for Teaching of Teacher Educators with respect to Gender

Table-1 shows the t-value to compare the mean score of preparation and planning for teaching of male and female teacher educators working in teacher education colleges. The t-value is found to be 3.99, which is significant at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. It is concluded that the male and female teacher educators differ significantly in their preparation and planning for teaching. The preparation and planning for teaching is high for the female teacher educators than the male teacher educators.

Comparison of Mean Difference in the Classroom Management of Teacher Educators with respect to Gender

Table-1 shows the t-value to compare the mean score of classroom management of male and female teacher educators working in teacher education colleges. The t-value is found to be 1.15, which is not significant at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. It is concluded that the male and female teacher educators do not differ significantly in their classroom management.

Comparison of Mean Difference in the Knowledge of Subject Matter of Teacher Educators with respect to Gender

Table-1 shows the t-value to compare the mean score of knowledge of subject matter of male and female teacher educators working in teacher education colleges. The t-value is found to be 6.62, which is significant at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. It is concluded that the male and female teacher educators differ significantly in their knowledge of subject matter. The knowledge of subject matter is high for the female teacher educators than the male teacher educators.

Comparison of Mean Difference in the Teacher Characteristics of Teacher Educators with respect to Gender

Table-1 shows the t-value to compare the mean score of teacher characteristics of male and female teacher educators working in teacher education colleges. The t-value is found to be 0.53, which is not significant at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. It is concluded that the male and female teacher educators do not differ significantly in their teacher characteristics.

Comparison of Mean Difference in the Interpersonal Relation of Teacher Educators with respect to Gender

Table-1 shows the t-value to compare the mean score of interpersonal relation of male and female teacher educators working in teacher education colleges. The t-value is found to be 3.49, which is significant at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. It is concluded that the male and female teacher educators differ significantly in their Interpersonal relation. The interpersonal relation is high for the female teacher educators than the male teacher educators.

Comparison of Mean Difference in the Total Teacher Effectiveness Score of Teacher Educators with respect to Gender

Table-1 shows the t-value to compare the mean score of total teacher effectiveness of male and female teacher educators working in teacher education colleges. The t-value is found to be 2.39, which is significant at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. It is concluded that the male and female teacher educators differ significantly in their total teacher effectiveness score. The total teacher effectiveness is high for the female teacher educators than the male teacher educators.

6. FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

1. The male and female teacher educators differ significantly in the total teacher effectiveness and the female teacher educators have high level of total teacher effectiveness than the male teacher educators.
2. The male and female teacher educators do not differ significantly in two dimensions of teacher effectiveness such as, class room management and teacher characteristics.
3. The male and female teacher educators differ significantly in three dimensions of teacher effectiveness such as preparation and planning for teaching, knowledge of subject matter, and interpersonal relation and in all these three dimensions the female teacher educators have high level than the male teacher educators.

7. CONCLUSION

The present study revealed that the total teacher effectiveness and its dimensions such as, preparation and planning for teaching, knowledge of subject matter, and interpersonal relation is high for the female teacher educators than the male teacher educators. It may be the reason that the female teacher educators are more serious about teaching in classroom than the male teacher educators. From the literature review Visweswari et al. (2019), Roy et al. (2018), Reddy (2017) also found that there were gender differences in relation to teacher effectiveness. Hence, the teacher education colleges should focus on identify those male teacher educators who perform poor continuously in their classroom, and take action to motivate and give the opportunity to grow up as professional practitioner. The male teacher educator can use the best practices in their classroom and institutions they are working or assimilating as human resource. According to the National Education Policy (2020), twenty hours is needed for professional development of higher education teachers. So that they can attend various types of workshops, FDP, CPD programmes, training programmes organized by UGC, ICSSR, PMMM-NMTT, University HRDC department and so on to enhance teacher effectiveness.

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